

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13842321>

COMPLEX THERAPY OF ORAL CANDIDIASIS AMONG PATIENTS WITH IMMUNODEFICIENCY DISEASES

Tahirova Kamola Abrarovna
Mirzakhodjaeva Nigina Firdavsova
Tashkent State Dental Institute
nigina.mf@mail.ru

ABSTRACT

Oral candidiasis, commonly referred to as “thrush,” involves infections of the tongue and other areas of the oral mucosa and is characterized by fungal overgrowth and invasion of superficial tissues. Oral candidiasis is a common fungal infection that affects the oral mucosa and is mainly caused by Candida albicans. Depending on the state of the host’s defense system and the state of the oral microflora, Candida can transform from a harmless commensal into a pathogenic organism that causes oral infection of the mucous membranes. Antifungal drugs are the mainstay of treatment for oral candidiasis in adults. These medications are designed to kill or inhibit the growth of Candida fungus. Probiotics have the potential to modulate the oral immune response to candidiasis. Their ability to enhance local immunity, reduce inflammation and regulate the immune response makes them a promising tool for both the treatment and prevention of oral candidiasis.

Key words: oral candidiasis, probiotics, antifungal drugs, thrush, Candida albicans.

Relevance of the problem. Oral candidiasis (OCOC), commonly referred to as “thrush,” involves infections of the tongue and other areas of the oral mucosa and is characterized by fungal overgrowth and invasion of superficial tissues [1,2,3]. Oral candidiasis is one of the common fungal infections that affects the oral mucosa and is caused mainly by the species Candida albicans [2, 4, 7]. Candida albicans was first isolated by Bennet (1844) from the sputum of a tuberculosis patient [5, 10, 15]. Candida albicans is part of the normal microflora of the human oral cavity; from 30% to 50% of people are carriers of this microorganism [8,9,11,20]. Predisposing factors that increase the risk of candidal infection include xerostomia, local trauma,

malnutrition, use of broad-spectrum antibiotics, long-term use of dentures, and HIV-infected people [6, 19].

Antifungal drugs are the main treatment for oral candidiasis in adults. These drugs are designed to kill or inhibit the growth of the fungus *Candida albicans* that causes this disease. In the treatment of oral candidiasis, various forms of antifungals are used: gels, creams, mouth rinses and oral medications.

Antifungals such as nystatin, miconazole, and clotrimazole are often used successfully to treat oral candidiasis. They show good results in eliminating clinical symptoms and treating infection. To achieve maximum effectiveness, it is important to follow your doctor's recommendations and take your medications as prescribed. Typically, the course of treatment can vary from several days to several weeks depending on the severity of the infection [12, 13, 14, 15].

Although effective, CSOPR may recur in some patients after completion of treatment. This occurs due to the fungus being resistant to drugs or due to insufficient duration of treatment. It is worth noting that in most cases antifungal drugs are well tolerated, but rare cases of allergic reactions or irritation may occur when applied topically [12, 16, 20].

In general, antifungal drugs are an effective treatment for CSOP. However, in case of relapse or lack of effectiveness of drugs, consultation with a specialist may be required to adjust treatment tactics [16, 17, 18]. Traditional methods of treating CSOPR have some limitations and disadvantages that are important to consider when using them:

1. Risk of developing resistance to antifungal drugs.

Long-term and frequent use of antifungal drugs may contribute to the development of resistance of the fungal pathogen to these drugs. This may reduce the effectiveness of medications and complicate treatment.

2. Possible side effects.

Although most antifungal drugs are usually well tolerated, some patients may experience side effects such as allergic reactions, irritation at the site of application, disharmony of microflora in the body, etc.

3. Limited duration of treatment.

Short-term effects: Some courses of treatment with antifungal drugs are limited in time due to the risk of side effects or the possible development of resistance. This may limit the drugs' ability to completely eliminate infection.

4. Possible relapses.

In some patients, after completing a course of treatment, oral candidiasis may recur, especially if the duration of treatment is insufficient or the effectiveness of treatment is incomplete.

5. Ineffectiveness in combating factors that cause candidiasis:

Traditional treatment methods focus on destroying the fungus, but do not always address the cause of candidiasis, such as immune disorders, antibiotic use, chronic diseases and other factors. Probiotics, when consumed in sufficient quantities, have a positive effect on the body, including the microflora of the oral cavity. These beneficial bacteria help promote health and maintain microflora balance, which can have a significant impact on your overall health.

Types of probiotics:

1. Lactobacillus. It is one of the most famous genera of probiotic bacteria. Lactobacillus acidophilus, Lactobacillus reuteri, Lactobacillus salivarius some of the well-known species of this genus.

2. Bifidobacterium. A common genus of probiotics that includes Bifidobacterium lactis, bifidum and longum.

3. Streptococcus. Some strains of Streptococcus may also have probiotic properties, including Streptococcus salivarius.

Mechanisms of action of probiotics in the oral microbiota:

1. Competition with pathogens: Probiotics compete with pathogens for nutrients and space, which interferes with pathogen colonization.

2. Production of Antimicrobial Substances: Some probiotics are capable of producing antimicrobial compounds that can kill or inhibit the growth of pathogenic bacteria and fungi.

3. Modulation of the immune system: Probiotics can affect the immune system, helping to strengthen the body's defenses and prevent the development of infections.

Potential effects on oral microflora:

· *Strengthen the microbiota:* Probiotics can help increase the number of beneficial bacteria in the mouth, which helps maintain a healthy microbiota.

· *Improved gum health:* Probiotics may also have a beneficial effect on gum health by reducing inflammation and maintaining gum health.

Probiotics represent a potentially useful tool for maintaining oral microbiota health. However, further research is needed to more accurately determine the effectiveness and optimal dosages of probiotics, as well as to clarify their specific effects on the oral microbiota in different conditions and body conditions.

Probiotics have the potential to modulate the oral immune response to candidiasis. Their ability to enhance local immunity, reduce inflammation and regulate the immune response makes them a good tool for the treatment and prevention of oral

candidiasis. However, further research is required to more accurately determine the mechanisms of action and optimal regimens for the use of probiotics.

Using probiotics to treat candidiasis may have a number of potential advantages over traditional treatments. Here are a few of them:

1. **Natural Effects:** Probiotics are naturally occurring living microorganisms found in the human body or nature. Their use is aimed at restoring the oral microbiota and the balance of beneficial and harmful bacteria.

2. **Less likely to develop resistance:** Unlike antibiotics, probiotics are less likely to cause resistance in microorganisms, meaning their long-term use is less likely to cause pathogenic bacteria to develop resistance to the probiotics.

3. **Less chance of side effects:** Probiotics are generally well tolerated by the body, and patients receiving probiotics experience a lower incidence of side effects compared to some traditional treatments such as antibiotics.

4. **Support Overall Health:** Probiotics not only help treat infection, but also support healthy oral flora, which can have a beneficial effect on overall oral and body health.

5. **Possibility of use as a prophylactic:** Probiotics can also be used as a prophylactic agent to prevent the occurrence of relapses of oral candidiasis, reducing the likelihood of developing infection in susceptible populations.

However, it is worth noting that the effectiveness of probiotics in the treatment of oral candidiasis requires further research to determine the optimal strains of probiotics, their dosages and application regimens. Some cases of candidiasis may require a multidisciplinary approach using both probiotics and other treatments to achieve optimal results.

Purpose of the study. To study the role of the use of probiotics in complex therapy of oral candidiasis.

Material and methods. During the study, we examined 50 patients diagnosed with candidiasis of the oral mucosa. The group of patients included patients aged from 22 to 65 years (average age was 54.3 ± 1.8 years).

The criteria for including patients in the study were the presence of a clinically and microbiologically confirmed diagnosis of oral mucosa candidiasis, age from 20 to 65 years, and informed consent of the patient to undergo the examination. Exclusion criteria were: dental anomalies and deformities; extended defects in the dentition; availability of orthodontic devices; the presence of infectious diseases (tuberculosis, HIV infection, severe concomitant pathology, tumors of any location; myocardial infarction, angina pectoris III, IV; KCM - II, III functional classes), the presence of a pacemaker; endocrine pathology (diabetes mellitus, thyrotoxicosis); the presence of a complicated allergic history in relation to drugs in the treatment regimen for CPR OB;

pregnancy and lactation, as well as the patient's refusal to undergo examination. When interviewing patients, attention was paid to complaints, the nature of the course, duration of the disease, and identification of possible causes of the occurrence of CPR of the oral mucosa. The condition of the oral mucosa, the nature and presence of specific elements of the lesion, and the severity of inflammatory and destructive processes in the epithelium of the oral mucosa were assessed. To confirm the diagnosis, smears were taken for microbiological examination. The diagnosis of "candidal stomatitis" was made in the presence of complaints, a clinical picture, the number of fungi of the genus *Candida* when inoculating >500 CFU/ml of swab swab, according to the results of microscopy of a smear with the presence of filaments of pseudomycelium or 10–15 or more yeast cells in the field of view [22].

Taking into account the method of treatment, patients were randomly divided into 2 groups. The main group included 27 people (women - 12, men - 15, average age - 54.9 ± 15.6 years), and the comparison group consisted of 23 people (women - 13, men - 10, average age - 55.1 ± 15.6 years).

Patients in the comparison group received only traditional antifungal therapy, which included the administration of the fluconazole-containing drug Fucis 150 mg orally, once a day, taken on days 1 and 3. Oral irrigation was also prescribed with a solution of the antiseptic Chlorhexidine.

In addition to basic antifungal therapy, including taking the drug Fucis (150 mg) once a day on the first and third days of treatment, patients in the main group were prescribed a course of probiotics. The drug of choice was the domestically produced drug Baktolor. It was prescribed 1 sachet 1 time per day, preferably at night before bedtime. After taking a probiotic, it is recommended not to eat or drink for at least 40 minutes.

Results and discussions. The results of a microscopic examination of smears taken from patients in both the main and control groups showed the presence of fungi of the genus *Candida*, as well as other microorganisms. Among the main clinical signs of candidiasis of the oral mucosa, in first place was the complaint of a coated tongue - plaque - in 92% of those examined. Pain and a burning sensation when eating were noted by 62% and 42% of patients, respectively. Inflammation of the red border of the lips and the presence of erythema in the corners of the mouth were found in only a third of all patients we examined. Almost half of all patients participating in the study complained of cracks and dry mouth. The average value of the results of microscopic examination of patients diagnosed with candidiasis of the oral mucosa was 2600 ± 160 CFU/ml of saliva. Considering that normally the value of this study should not exceed 100 CFU/ml, our results indicate that the patients we examined were diagnosed with candidiasis of the oral mucosa.

During a bacterioscopic examination after completion of the course of treatment, *Candida* fungi were detected in single quantities in smears from the oral mucosa of patients in the control and main groups, mainly mature old forms of mycelium. The presence of other microorganisms decreased significantly, mainly coccal flora was detected.

The microbiological research method showed that this disease in most cases occurs in a chronic form. Comparison of the number of colony-forming units detected during bacteriological examination also convincingly showed the feasibility of using antioxidants. In the control group, after a course of standard therapy, this indicator decreased only to 860 ± 100 CFU, and in the main group, whose patients additionally took antioxidants - to 500 ± 80 CFU ($p < 0.01$). The microbiological research method showed that this disease in most cases occurs in a chronic form. Comparison of the number of colony-forming units detected during bacteriological examination also convincingly showed the feasibility of using probiotics.

Conclusion. Thus, our study confirmed the positive effect of the use of probiotics in complex therapy of patients with a confirmed diagnosis of candidiasis of the oral mucosa. Probiotics represent a potentially useful tool for maintaining the health of the oral microbiota, increasing the rate of tissue epithelialization in patients diagnosed with oral candidiasis, and reducing the incidence of relapse in patients with this diagnosis.

Literature

1. Khalilova U. A., Tumarenko A. V., Skvortsov V. V. Oral candidiasis and its local therapy //Medical nurse. – 2019. – T. 21. – No. 7. – pp. 16-21.
2. Khasanova, L., Yunuskhodzhaeva, M., Rustamova, M. Combination therapy for candidiasis of the oral mucosa. //Journal of Dentistry and Craniofacial Research, 2022.- 2(2), 22–24.
3. Yunuskhodzhaeva M., Rustamova M. Improving the principles of treatment of patients with fungal and bacterial-fungal stomatitis under the basis of a removable laminar denture with complete absence of teeth // Journal of Dentistry and Craniofacial Research. – 2021. – T. 2. – No. 2. – pp. 62-64.
4. Fakhim H, Vaezi A, Javidnia J, Nasri E, Mahdi D, Diba K, Badali H. *Candida africana* vulvovaginitis: Prevalence and geographical distribution. //J Mycol Med. 2020 Sep;30(3):100966.
5. Garcia-Cuesta C, Sarrion-Perez MG, Bagan JV. Current treatment of oral candidiasis: A literature review. J Clin Exp Dent.2014; 6(5):e576-82

6. Lewis MAO, Williams DW. Diagnosis and management of oral candidosis. //Br Dent J. 2017 Nov 10;223(9):675-681.
7. Manik A, Bahl R. A review on oral candidal infection. J Adv Med Dent Sci Res. 2017;5(3):54-57
8. Parslow BY, Thornton CR. Continuing Shifts in Epidemiology and Antifungal Susceptibility Highlight the Need for Improved Disease Management of Invasive Candidiasis. //Microorganisms. 2022 Jun 13;10(6):1208.
9. Patel M. Oral Cavity and Candida albicans: Colonization to the Development of Infection. //Pathogens. 2022 Mar 10;11(3):335.
10. Patel PN, Sah P, Chandrashekar C, Vidyasagar S, Venkata Rao J, Tiwari M, Radhakrishnan R. Oral candidal speciation, virulence and antifungal susceptibility in type 2 diabetes mellitus. Diabetes Res Clin Pract. 2017 Mar;125:10-19.
11. Patil A, Susmitha HR, Basappa S. Drug-induced Oral Candidiasis: A Case Report. IJSS Case Reports & Reviews 2016;2(12):1-4
12. Peixoto LR, Rosalen PL, Ferreira GLS, et al. Antifungal activity, mode of action and anti-biofilm effects of Laurus nobilis Linnaeus essential oil against Candida spp. //Arch Oral Biol. 2017;73:179–185.
13. Peng DS, Lo CH, Tseng YL, Kuo SL, Chiang CP, Chiang ML. Efficacy of oral nystatin treatment for patients with oral mucosal dysesthesia but without objective oral mucosal manifestations and necessity of Candida culture test before oral nystatin treatment. //J Dent Sci. 2022 Oct;17(4):1802-1813.
14. Rautemaa R, Ramage G. Oral candidosis—clinical challenges of a biofilm disease. Crit Rev Microbiol. 2011 Nov;37(4):328-36.
15. Richardson R, Antilla VJ. Suun hiivainfektioiden diagnostiikka ja hoitoperiaatteet [Diagnosis and treatment of oral candidosis].// Duodecim. 2010;126(2):174-80.
16. Rodero CF, Fioramonti Calixto GM, Cristina Dos Santos K, et al. Curcumin-loaded liquid crystalline systems for controlled drug release and improved treatment of vulvovaginal candidiasis. Mol Pharm. 2018;15(10):4491–4504.
17. Romo JA, Pierce CG, Chaturvedi AK, Lazzell AL, McHardy SF, Saville SP, Lopez-Ribot JL. Development of Anti-Virulence Approaches for Candidiasis via a Novel Series of Small-Molecule Inhibitors of Candida albicans Filamentation. mBio. 2017 Dec 5;8(6):e01991-17.
18. Sankari SL, Gayathri K, Balachander N, et al. Candida in potentially malignant oral disorders. J Pharm Bioall Sci. 2015;7:S 162- 4.
19. Singh A, Verma R, Murari A, et al. Oral candidiasis: An overview. J Oral Maxillofac Pathol. 2014;18:81-5.
20. Williams D, Lewis M. Pathogenesis and treatment of oral candidiasis. J Oral Microbiol. 2011;3:1-11.